

Research Article

***Vaccinium lallanii*, a replacement name for *V. paludicola* Sleumer (Ericaceae)**

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Article Details: Received: 2025-03-25 | Accepted: 2025-07-22 | Available online: 2025-07-25

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Abstract: A new name, *Vaccinium lallanii* R.Kr.Singh, is proposed herein to replace the illegitimate name *V. paludicola* Sleumer, being a later homonym of *V. paludicola* Camp (Ericaceae).

Keywords: Endemic, Illegitimate, Indonesia, Later homonym, Sulawesi, *Vaccinium paludicola*

Introduction

The genus *Vaccinium* L. is represented by about 488 species worldwide (POWO, 2025). In Sulawesi, Indonesia, the genus is represented by 15 species and 2 varieties, namely *V. aucupis* Sleumer, *V. centrocelebicum* Sleumer var. *centrocelebicum*, *V. centrocelebicum* var. *majus* Sleumer, *V. contractum* Sleumer, *V. cuneifolium* (Blume) Miq., *V. dubiosum* J.J.Sm., *V. kjellbergii* J.J.Sm., *V. latissimum* J.J.Sm., *V. lucidum* (Blume) Miq., *V. paludicola* Sleumer var. *paludicola*, *V. paludicola* var. *hirsutulum* Mustaqim, *V. pilosilobum* J.J.Sm., *V. sclerophyllum* Sleumer, *V. sulawesiense* Mustaqim & P.W.Fritsch, *V. timorensis* Fawc., *V. tomicipes* J.J.Sm. and *V. warburgii* Sleumer, of which all except *V. lucidum* and *V. timorensis* are endemic to Sulawesi. However, the name *V. paludicola* Sleumer (1961: 53) is illegitimate because it is a later homonym of *V. paludicola* Camp (1942: 219) in accordance with Article 53.1 of the ICN (Turland et al., 2018). Therefore, a replacement name *V. lallanii* is proposed herein. Furthermore, the variety *hirsutulum* of *V. paludicola*, described from Sulawesi by Mustaqim (in Mustaqim & Ardi, 2019), is transferred as *V. lallanii* var. *hirsutulum*.

Nomenclature

Vaccinium lallanii R.Kr.Singh, *nom. nov.*

Figure 1: Holotype of *Vaccinium paludicola* Sleumer (L0008172, © Naturalis Biodiversity Center, Leiden)

Figure 2: Isotype of *Vaccinium paludicola* Sleumer (A00016024, © Herbarium of the Arnold Arboretum, Harvard University)

Figure 3: Isotype of *Vaccinium paludicola* Sleumer (BO-189586, © Herbarium Bogoriense)

≡ *Vaccinium paludicola* Sleumer, Blumea 11: 53. 1961, *nom. illeg., non* Camp, Brittonia 4: 219. 1942.

Holotype: Indonesia, Celebes (Sulawesi), Central Sulawesi province, Kolonedale, between saddle and eastern slope of the Tomongkobaë group, 9 October 1938, *P.J. Eyma* 3957 (L0008172!), Figure 1); isotypes A00016024! (Figure 2), BO-189586! (Figure 3), U0106452!.

Distribution: Endemic to Indonesia (Sulawesi).

Etymology: Named after my father late Shri Lallan Singh.

Vaccinium lallanii* var. *hirsutulum (Mustaqim) R.Kr.Singh, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Vaccinium paludicola* var. *hirsutulum* Mustaqim in Telopea 22: 201, f. 5 & 6. 2019.

Holotype: Indonesia, Central Sulawesi, Poso Regency, Tentena-Bada road divide, 1 August 2018, *W.H. Ardi* 263 (BO); isotype CEB.

Distribution: Endemic to Indonesia (Sulawesi).

Notes: Mustaqim & Ardi (2019) distinguished *Vaccinium paludicola* var. *hirsutulum* from the typical variety, *V. paludicola* Sleumer var. *paludicola*, based on some morphological features. The variety *hirsutulum* has hirsutulous abaxial leaf surfaces, corolla with hirsutulous hairs outside, and style with few longish hairs at the base, whereas the typical variety is entirely glabrous in these parts. Additionally, the filaments in var. *hirsutulum* are alternately 5 mm and 4 mm long, compared to 2.7 mm and 2 mm in var. *paludicola*, supporting its recognition as a distinct variety.

Acknowledgements

The author is thankful to the Director, Botanical Survey of India, Kolkata, and Head of Office, Botanical Survey of India, Arid Zone Regional Centre, Jodhpur, for the facilities. I am also grateful to the curators of A, BO, L, and U for the images and information of type specimens.

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